

DISTRIBUTION OF THE SPARINGLY SOLUBLE SALTS IN PERIODIC STRUCTURES. PART II

BY M. C. RASTOGI

Liesegang rings of six different substances have been analysed with a view to ascertaining the amount of sparingly soluble salts in the rings and in the clear spaces or in the alternate bands where there occur no clear spaces.

In a previous communication (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 125) it has been shown that the amount of the sparingly soluble salts per gram of gel in the case of rings separated by clear spaces differs widely, while in the case of alternate bands of precipitates separated by bands of peptised sol, the amount is almost the same. This study has been extended further, in order to obtain a more comprehensive idea about the distribution of the sparingly soluble salts in the bands of each type.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental method is the same as given in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*). 5% Gelatin or 1% agar-agar was used. Gel solutions containing 1 g. barium and mercuric chloride and silver nitrate per 100 g. of the solution were prepared and poured into a series of tubes. After the gel had set 30%, 20% and 10% normal sodium phosphate, potassium iodide, sodium thiosulphate, potassium ferrocyanide, and 10%, 5% and 2.5% sodium borate and ammonium molybdate were allowed to diffuse from the top of the tubes. The rings were analysed after two weeks. The following device for removing the gel was used. The corks at the top of the tubes were removed and the diffusing electrolyte was poured back. Then the tubes were dipped in water at about 80° for a second or two as the case might be. This had the effect of loosening the gel adhering to the glass and the entire structure could be easily slipped on the glass plate. The structures were then cut separately into rings and clear spaces or in bands by means of a safety razor blade and analysed. The results of the analysis of both types of rings are given below.

Type I: Rings separated by clear spaces

TABLE I

Barium phosphate rings in agar-agar

Distribution of Ba as BaSO ₄ in rings and clear spaces:					
No.	Ring or space.	Wt. of ring or space.	Wt. of BaSO ₄ .	Wt. per g.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Ring	0.4430 g.	0.0114 g.	0.0257	3.57
2	Ring	0.3096	0.0144	0.0465	6.47
3	Ring	0.3710	0.0154	0.0416	5.80
4	Clear space	0.1724	0.0012	0.0072	1.00
5	Clear space	0.3434	0.0026	0.0075	1.04

Type II: Banded structure in the otherwise Continuous Precipitate

TABLE II

Mercuric iodide bands in agar-agar.
Distribution of Hg as HgS in bands:

No.	Band.	Wt. of band.	Wt. of HgS.	Wt. per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Red	0.2240 g.	0.0008 g.	0.0035 g.	1.00
2	Yellow	0.2256	0.0008	0.0035	1.00
3	Red	0.2128	0.0010	0.0047	1.34

TABLE III

Silver thiosulphate bands in gelatin.
Distribution of Ag as AgCl in bands:

No.	Band.	Wt. of band.	Wt. of AgCl.	Wt. per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Black	1.1010 g.	0.0178 g.	0.162 g.	1.05
2	Grey	0.5873	0.0090	0.154	1.00
3	Black	0.5508	0.0080	0.0156	1.01
4	Grey	0.4092	0.0064	0.0157	1.02

TABLE IV

Silver ferrocyanide bands in gelatin.
Distribution of Ag as AgCl in bands:

No.	Band.	Wt. of band.	Wt. of AgCl.	Wt. per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Whitish	0.4712 g.	0.0076 g.	0.0161 g.	1.42
2	Bluish	0.1300	0.0016	0.0123	1.08
3	Whitish	0.3084	0.0036	0.0119	1.05
4	Bluish	0.1066	0.0012	0.0113	1.00

TABLE V

Silver molybdate bands in gelatin.
Distribution of Ag as AgCl in bands:

No.	Band.	Wt. of band.	Wt. of AgCl.	Wt. per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	White	0.1850 g.	0.0088 g.	0.0476 g.	1.30
2	Black	0.2208	0.0102	0.0452	1.24
3	White	0.2198	0.0106	0.0482	1.32
4	Black	0.2532	0.0092	0.0364	1.00

TABLE VI

Silver borate bands in gelatin.
Distribution of Ag as AgCl in bands:

No.	Band.	Wt. of band.	Wt. of AgCl.	Wt. per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g of gel.
1	Black	0.4068 g.	0.0074 g	0.0182	1.14
2	White	0.3824	0.0068	0.0178	1.11
3	Black	0.2306	0.0058	0.0251	1.59
4	White	0.5586	0.0080	0.0159	1.00

DISCUSSION

Two types of rings have been given by Dhar and Chatterji and co-workers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 31, 15; 1925, 37, 2, 89; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 20, 41). The claim of supersaturation theory to explain the rings separated by clear spaces which belong to the periodic structures of the first type can be understood, but theories fail to explain the second type of bands. It may be argued that after the release of supersaturation, the clear space is saturated with sparingly soluble substance or, on the other hand, according to adsorption theory, the incomplete or partial adsorption of the solute by the precipitate may leave some of it near the precipitate to produce scanty deposits instead of complete absence of the sparingly soluble salt. Hence, two consecutive rings will not be separated by absolutely clear spaces, but these clear spaces will be contaminated more or less by the sparingly soluble salt. The net result will be that the amount of the sparingly soluble salt per gram of gel in alternate bands will not be equal, but it will vary as in the case of rings separated by clear spaces. But this is not actually the case, the alternate bands contain almost equal amounts of the sparingly soluble salt. The more feasible explanation of the phenomenon was offered by coagulation theory of Dhar and Chatterji (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 41). According to them, the second type of banded structures are produced by the substances which have the property of not adsorbing their own sol and hence alternate bands of precipitate and of peptised sol are formed. Therefore, the amount of the sparingly soluble salt per gram of gel in alternate bands will almost be the same, while in the case of the first type, the amount will vary widely. The results, obtained here, support the above view, as rings of barium phosphate, which belongs to the first type, the amount of the precipitate per gram of gel varies widely from those in the clear spaces, while in the cases of mercuric iodide, silver borate, silver molybdate and silver ferrocyanide structures, which belong to the second type, the sparingly soluble substances in both the bands are almost the same.

The author's thanks are due to Dr. A. C. Chatterji for helpful guidance.